

THE BENEFITS OF FIESTA IN THE PHILIPPINES

Jayrome Lleva Nuñez

Introduction

Energetic marching bands, processions of patron saints, sumptuous foods, lively parades, colorful floats, vibrant costumes, amateur singing or dancing competitions, competitive street dancing showdowns, beauty pageants, miss gay competitions, local makeshift shopping stores that come from different parts of the province, and many more. These are just some of the views that a Filipino fiesta has. Fiestas has been a long tradition that we got from our ancestors even before our Spanish colonizers arrived, they are rooted with religious beliefs of thanking the village's (or town) patron saint or deities for blessing the place with abundance of resources. Fiestas also show some traditions of offering nature as a way of gratitude or sacrifice.

Fiestas are celebrated from the smallest level of governmental body (*barangay*/village) to national level. In this essay, I will be discussing the benefits of fiesta from different levels of society in our country; national, provincial/city, and *barangay* level.

National level fiesta

The Mother of all Philippine Festivals also known as the *Aliwan Fiesta*. This is a national level of fiesta celebration where all major regional festivals participate to compete and have fun in the capital of the country – Manila.

I have been an avid fan of watching this festival because I can watch colorful floats and different festival groups from all over the country gather in one place. The celebration is grand and extravagant! This festival allows

people to eyewitness the diversity of Philippines. Creativity flourishes along the Roxas Boulevard (Pasay City), spectators flock the pavements, traffic jams are unimaginable, and local street food sellers are thriving during this event. This event has been one of the highlights of every summer not just to locals but also to foreign visitors.

Provincial / City fiestas

These fiestas are well and alive to every province in every corner of our country. Either they are deeply rooted to tradition or shaped by the local government. As time goes by these provincial festivals are becoming more and more competitive that it attracts more tourists that help boost the region's economy. During these kinds of events also enable local towns or villages to show their unique products – this is also called *OTOP (One Town, One Product)*

OTOP enable local producers to improve their economy by selling good or closing deals to businesses as suppliers. Example, in Ilocos Sur (where I stayed for six years) many local producers were able to advance their crafts because of the OTOP program and support provided by the LGU.

Regional fiestas are not just for tourists and local producers, it also taps the schools to participate in competition which enable the learners to explore and display their talents. Festivals also boost local economy because of expenditures during events, concerts, shopping, food, and tourism.

Barangay fiesta

Village fiesta is more interesting because it when locals prepare food in their houses and invite people to visit and dine with them. Local amateur contests and parlor games are still common to this kind of celebrations. These kinds of celebrations are still well and alive in many parts of our country.

This kind of fiesta enables local villagers to socialize, have fun, and celebrate each year's blessings. People decorating the plaza for the *sayawan sa barangay*, *banderitas* on the streets are flashed signifying the spirit of festivity are just some of the events you will see in every barangay.

Final thoughts

Regardless of celebration level, fiesta is beneficial emotionally and economically to many of us. It gives avenue to our local producers to exhibit their products and generate income. This also enable schools to showcase their talents by participating in events and competitions. This also attracts foreign and local tourism to explore the beauty of our homeland. And most importantly, it gives our identity because of our diverse culture and tradition.

References

- Ethnic Groups Philippines. (2017, April 21). Aliwan Fiesta – The Mother of All Festivals. Retrieved from <http://www.ethnicgroupsphilippines.com/2017/04/27/aliwan-fiesta-the-mother-of-all-festivals/>
- Lewis, S. (2016, March 30). Community Festivals - Big Benefits and Economic Drivers. Retrieved from <https://www.lewissears.com/2016/03/30/community-festivals-big-benefits-and-economic-drivers/>
- Landicho, E. C. (2019, May 15). Why Fiestas are Important to Filipinos. Retrieved from <https://www.philippinesinsider.com/events-festivals-holidays/why-fiestas-are-important-to-filipinos/>
- Local, R. (2017, August 18). The Importance of Festivals Within Your Community. Retrieved from <https://www.houstonparty.com/importance-festivals-within-community/>
- Malajito, Y., & Chang, M. (2019, April 25). LOOK: Pasalubong cheat sheet to Ilocos Sur. Retrieved from <https://nolisoli.ph/61512/ilocos-sur-yamalajito-20190422/>
- Shrusti, S. (2018, September 28). Social Benefits of Celebrating Festivals Together in Township. Retrieved from <http://www.swapnasrushti.co.in/blog/social-benefits-of-festivals-celebration/>